
Literature Review: The Impact of Syrian Refugees on Turkey's Policy

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ABSTRACT:

The Syrian refugee's presence in Turkey has attracted the attention of researchers in international relations field. The impact of Syrian refugees in Turkey has been studied from different scopes. However, there were not many studies available regarding the impact of the Syrian refugees on Turkey's policy especially in the context of the EU-Turkish Agreement 2016. This paper reviews about one decade of researched available on the impact of the Syrian refugees in Turkey internally and externally that the researchers may utilize with main focus on Turkey's policy against the European Opinion countries.

Keywords: Syrian Refugees, Impact, Policy, EU.

Introduction:

The Syrian refugees in Turkey fled their lives from the Syrian revolution that started in 2011. This existence of a big number imposes several impacts not only on Turkey, but also the European countries. The European Union managed to sign an agreement with the Turkish government in 2016. The agreement went into several fields including stopping the refugees from flooding to the EU. As result of this agreement, Turkey started new policies internally and externally. Many researchers have conducted research regarding this issue. This paper tries to review the available literature regarding the impact of the Syrian refugees on Turkey's policy in the context of Turkish-EU agreement 2016.

1. Amer, Nariman, et al, (2013). *Factors of Civil Peace and Civil conflict in Syria*. Center of Civil Society and Democracy in Syria.

The authors tried to detect the actual factors of peace in the Syrian society. They are targeting the period of the Syrian crisis. Not only the refugees issued solution they seek, but also other fields such as the political reform, social justice and human right. They determined the factors of civil peace in aid solidarity, people's unity, the role of religion's men, forming civil government, and refugees return home from Diaspora, etc. In the other hand they pointed out the civil conflict factor in some important points like denying the other political partners, the continuation of refugees' crisis in the neighboring counties, the cast revenge and the absence of democracy.

The Syrian revolution that is happening is an attempt to impose a fundamental change that includes all aspects of life, politically, socially and economically. As the Syrian crisis is going on it bring to the society unwanted results. Human right violations, bloodshed, new thoughts, war and peace are natural outcomes of any military conflict.

The previous Arab Spring scenarios that happened before the Syrian crisis affected the Syrian hardly. This is what forced the people to flee. Killing in Iraq is a close example of what would be happen to them. Terrorist groups are spread everywhere in Syrian. Violence is the main characteristic of each partner of the crisis, even the governments like the Syrian official militaries practicing violence.

Settling the refugees down inside Syria or in Turkey, Lebanon or Jordan is a big dilemma. The Palestinian refugees had been settled down in Jordan. They became Jordanians with full civil rights. Is it going to be done again for the Syrians in Turkey, Lebanon and Jordan?

Also the refugees are a source of trouble for the hosting countries. Some of them have relations with the partners of the crisis. Even inside Syria, the new temporary used lands for housing will cost the government lot of money to provide basic services. This thing is a block in the developing process which is stopping now.

The book is helpful for my synopsis because it shows the loss of education for a whole generation is another factor of instability in the future. They will be sink in the swamp of poverty, then ignorance, poverty, then the beginning of a new cycle of violence. The authors see that this issue has to take a priority in the agenda of the government for whom in Syria.

The authors are a group of researcher who work in several Syrian universities and research centers. They are specialized in the social issues of the Arab so cities. They give several points of views about the factors of the crisis and suggest solutions through scenarios.

2. Aras, Bulent, et al, (2012). *The Turkish Transforming towards the Arab Region*. Center of Middle East Studies. Amman.

Writers from Turkey and the Arab world are giving an analysis to the Turkish foreign policy towards the Arab region. They are starting with the components of the foreign policy of Turkey. Then they go deep into the factors of changing this policy. How it will affect the relations with the Arabs. The refugees in the Turkish land as a pushing card against the Syrian government.

The writers who are a group of Arab and Turkish scholars see that the relations issue with the EU is important for an integrated Middle East where people and goods can move freely. However, this integration project should not take place at the expense of the EU. There is a real Turkish need to adopt a long-term perspective on this issue and maintain commitment to the EU membership process. The EU will be important for Turkey for purely economic reasons too. The transition to democracy and rule of law in the Arab world will be a painful one. There will be ups and downs accompanied with considerable instability in the Turkish policy towards the Arabs because of economic and political interests.

During the transition period Turkish companies will need access to the Arab markets to make up for the losses incurred as a result of the uprisings and the accompanying instability. The Turkish-Arab compatibility with the EU factor always creates a problematic imbalance in foreign trade between Turkey and its neighborhood. Surveys showed that Turkey's market is an attractive partner for the Arab world.

This book is important because it shows that the growing Turkish influence in the Middle East and the Muslim world is boosting the country's significance for America and Europe as well as granting it much more flexibility away from Western attitudes than before, but without harming their relations. The new continuous shift in challenges for the policies of the partners and the security of the EU impose fundamental changes in the foreign policy of Ankara.

Turkey's role as an important regional player cannot be neglected. Others are there, USA, Arabs, EU, NATO, Russia, Iran, Israel and the Syrian crisis with refugees. Economic and political sequences of the civil war in Syria affect Turkey. So, how does Turkey look to the crisis in Syria? What to do in with refugees? The price of role of gate guard of Europe!

3. Bidinger, S., Lang, A., Hites, D., Kuzmova, Y., Noureddine, E., Akram, S. M., ... & Kistner, T. (2014). *Protecting Syrian Refugees: Laws, Policies, and Global Responsibility Sharing*. Boston: Boston University School of Law. Retrieved May, 25, 2015.

This work came out of the contribution of 43 institutions' staffs and officials of the following individuals, organizations and government ministries. It shows that the Syrian Civil war has caused approximately 2.7 million Syrians to leave their country since 2011, and double that many are expected to have fled Syria by the end of 2014. The Syrian refugee crisis has brought tremendous challenges to the region, and this research attempts to map out one aspect of the crisis that has received very little attention: that is, the laws and policies at the international, regional and domestic level affecting the rights and status of the refugees flooding out of Syria.

Turkey, the most stable host country, has already expended over \$2.5 billion on assisting refugees from Syria—a figure exceeding the entire EU contribution to the crisis thus far—and cannot by itself continue indefinitely to provide for the needs of the ever-growing refugee population coming over its long border with Syria.

Figures show that the countries currently hosting the vast majority of the refugee flow out of Syria are stretched to the limits of their resources. Jordan, Lebanon and Egypt have huge refugee populations pre-dating the Syrian influx. Many, if not most, of these preexisting refugee groups live in desperate conditions, and host countries cannot meet all the refugees' assistance and protection needs.

Lebanon and Egypt's unemployment rates are in the double-digits. Jordan is the fourth most water-stressed country in the world, with insufficient potable water for its own people. Lebanon and Egypt have extremely volatile political environments, and unstable governments. The Lebanese consider the Syrian conflict to have already crossed inside their territory and fear another civil war as a direct consequence if the war inside Syria is not halted soon.

Turkey, the most stable host country, has already expended over \$2.5 billion on assisting refugees from Syria—a figure exceeding the entire EU contribution to the crisis thus far—and cannot by itself continue indefinitely to provide for the needs of the ever-growing refugee population coming over its long border with Syria.

4. Cupolo, Diego. (2013). *SEVEN SYRIANS: War accounts from Syrian Refugees*. 8th House Publishing

The book "Seven Syrians - War Accounts from Syrian Refugees" which is written by the author Diego Cupolo captures the stories and struggles of those caught in the middle of the armed conflict currently ravaging Syria. Refugees' lives are the core of his book. There is a big gap between the demands of the refugees and the politicians in EU, Turkey, Syria and the international organizations. Big difference on what is in dreams and what is in reality. What future is waiting there?

The author is tracking the factors of the crisis since the growth was not felt uniformly, and by 2010 the youth unemployment rate was still around 20 percent. In 2011, discontent among Syrians in response to economic pressures and the lack of political reform reflected the mood elsewhere in the Middle East—Tunisia, Egypt, Yemen, Bahrain, and Libya—where popular protests had already begun to topple governments. In March, the so-called "Arab Spring" came to Syria, as children and teenagers in the city of Daraa were arrested for painting anti-government graffiti on the walls of a school.

When demonstrators demanded that they be released, the police cracked down and dozens of protesters were killed. The president, facing calls for his resignation, promised changes, but then the regime ordered troops into Daraa to clamp down on the protests. Since that time violence has increased between Assad's forces and rebel groups fighting to bring down the government. In July 2012 the Red Cross declared the conflict a civil war.

Over the years, the stalemated conflict became more violent and complex. The Free Syrian Army, led by generals who defected from Assad's army, does not fight government forces alone; al-Qaeda-linked jihadist fighters have also joined the effort. Meanwhile, the government is supported by Iran and Russia.

Framed by Diego Cupolo's unerring eye while touring the region, these photographs and first-hand accounts remind us that it is civilians who suffer the brunt of war's atrocities. In a series of humanizing portraits, Diego Cupolo takes us into the lives of those fortunate enough to have survived the conflict decimating their homeland. Forced to flee their homes and families, these men, women and children, teachers, plumbers, engineers, taxi drivers, brothers and sisters no different than ourselves and our neighbors, tell us in their own words of their struggles, triumphs, pains and fortitude and of the monstrosity of war when all of us the world over, seek the same security and opportunities for our children.

5. Eitah, Sameer, et al, (2012) *The Arabs and Turkey: Challenges of the Present and Reckonings of the Future*. Arab Center for Research & Policy Studies. Doha Institute.

This huge book is a result of the scientific conference held in Doha in 2011 under the title of *The Arabs and Turkey: Challenges of the Present and Reckonings of the Future*. The conference focused on important terms; historical-future relations; strategic policies, economy; energy and water. The researchers asked main questions. What does the Arabic-Turkish relation means for Arabs, coordination or confrontation? Does the Turkish political model fits for the Arab Fundamental Movements? And what are the expected coming changes in accordance with the crisis happening in Syria.

The book will help in put justifications for the Turkish foreign policy towards the Syrian civil war and the reflection of its action for the refugees.

The Arab writers are putting an important subject on the table, which is the Turkish model. The Turkish model is attracting Arabintellectuals. The Turkish Islam which have caught significant interest among the political circles in Turkey and the West but which failed to receive adequate attention from the academia. The authorswent through there are three main outlooks that conceptualize and idealize the Turkish model *vis-à-vis* its relation to Arab: nationalist, orientalist, and liberal. These perspectives depart from a set of assumptions and practical objectives in order to make their proposal appealing.

But, even for Arab thinkers who support the revolution against the Syrian ruler, Turkey's assertiveness has been progressively seen as ill-advised and perilous, leading to an escalation of the conflict. In particular, Turkey's support for the rebels, including the fringes identified as extremist has led many to wonder what exactly Ankara's political objective is in the Syrian civil war.

The concerns over Turkey's policy in the Middle East were further exacerbated in the falling of Arab dictators. The Turkish government has been one of the most vocal critics of latest developments in the region.

The authors are a group of Arab writers and researcher and intellectuals from several Arab countries. They tried to be very realistic in their papers.]

6. Kanat, K. B., & Üstün, K. (2015, April). *Turkey's Syrian refugees: Toward integration*. SETA.

This book is speaking about the Syrian conflict which produced the most compelling humanitarian challenge of the 21st century. According to the United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA), there are 12.2 million people in need of humanitarian assistance with 3.9 million who fled the country and 7.6 million internally displaced persons in Syria. With no end to the conflict in sight, these numbers simply continue to rise and the obstacles to resolving the crisis remain out of reach. Syria's neighbors are under great pressure to host the refugees and most of them struggle to respond adequately.

The book mentions that it is estimated that Turkey currently hosts around 2 million Syrian refugees who are, comparatively speaking, "better off" than refugees in other neighboring states. Turkey has done an exemplary job in hosting them and has received praise for its efforts by the international community.' In fact, the Turkish government and civil society have demonstrated nothing short of a "Herculean" effort in providing for the Syrian refugees over the past four years. Nevertheless, there remain serious short-term and long-term challenges ahead in ensuring the well-being of the refugees in countries neighboring Syria. This book is the result of a four month long research project conducted in Washington DC and in Turkey. In this book, the writer provide an overview of the situation of refugees in Turkey and the difficulties that Turkey is facing in handling such a major crisis alongside of its Southern border. We also assess the policy implications of this crisis for Turkey and the international community. We discuss Turkey's open-door policy, the camp and non-camp refugees, the legal framework, integration, the international community's response, and the impact on Turkish foreign policy choices. We end the report with a series of policy recommendations that we hope will help cope with this monumental task at hand and contribute to a better coordination between Turkey and the international community.

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KilicBugraKanat is the Research Director at the SETA Foundation at Washington DC. He is also an Assistant Professor of Political Science at Penn State University, Erie. Dr. Kanat received his PhD in Political Science from Syracuse University.

7. Mahfoud, Akil. (2012). *Syria-Turkey: Turning Point or Historical Bet*. Arab Center for Research & Policy Studies. Doha Institute.

The book consists of seven chapters. The first chapter is taking the turning point in the Syrian-Turkish relations. Is it a real turning point or confusion, or is it an introduction for a historical bet? The second chapter focuses on the historical bets of the Syrian-Turkish relation. The third chapter speaks about the Turkish general limitations regarding the Syrian crisis. The Turkish foreign policy toward the Syrian crisis actions and results such as the refugees and the military interventions is mentioned in the fourth chapter. The fifth chapter talks about the Turkish interpretations of the crisis. The

relation between Turkey and the opposition is discussed in the sixth chapter. Finally, the seventh chapter shows the possible coming scenarios from the Turkish perspective.

Turkey expressed its support for the protests, viewing them as political and peaceful expressions of the demands of democratic change and reform, and that the Syria should advocates reformist policies that must agree with the popular demands for change.

Refugees camps and the other side of the borders with Turkey became the scene of the broad media activism. The careful management of the refugees dossier as to make it a continual issue and avoiding serious coordination with the Syrian side; the Turkish Red Crescent has even refused to assist the Syrian Red Crescent in that regard. One of the refugees camp blocked the way of the international Red Cross team with boulders and gunfire when they attempted to enter the camp from the Syrian side of the borders. Such incident must be linked to a Turkish will that insists on being the exclusive gate to dealing with the dossier.

The book mentions several incidents to show that the Turks are having the command and the full control of the refugees' destinies. It shows that Turkey has adopted a complex position that international degree of opacity and that function on multiple levels. The Turkish discourse insinuates that Turkey supports the stability of the country, in all possible interpretations, to the point where supporting stability becomes the main objective and not the persistence of the political regime.

Akil Mahfoud is a Ph.D. holder in International Relations from Aleppo University. He worked in high positions in the Syrian government. He wrote several political books and articles.

8. Naser, R. Mahshi, Z. Abu Ismael, K. (2013) *The Syrian Crisis: Roots & Economical and Social Sequences*. Syrian Center for Policy Research.

The book is discussing the deep roots of the Syrian crisis. The first chapter is discussing the economical problem behind the crisis, the human and social factors and the institutional factors that lead to rage the crisis. Chapter two focuses on the demographical changes and economical sequences happening due to refugees and people movement internally and externally. The third chapter shows the governmental response to the huge movement of people. Also, the international aids are recorded. The book shows the effects of Syrian people socially and economically.

The importance of the book comes from that it shows how Syrian the peaceful and secular country is getting destroyed. Half the population is displaced; nearly one fifth are refugees abroad; an estimated 1 per cent of Syrians have died; and over half the population desperately requires humanitarian assistance. Whatever may be the reasons for the crisis, whoever may be responsible, the immediate need is to find a way to stop the violence. This is going to be a herculean task, given that there are groups, supported from abroad that are beyond the purview of international law.

Also the writers are drawing attention to the scale of this tragedy, commentators risk depriving it of context. It is but the latest - if the largest - in a series of refugee crises arising from the events that followed on from the arbitrary partition of the Arabic-speaking provinces of the Ottoman Empire by Britain and France after World War I.

That partition led to injustices intertwined with instability, which have played their part in incubating the Syrian tragedy. Before Syria descended into chaos in 2011, it had been forced - as had Jordan and Lebanon - to accommodate successive waves of destitute people fleeing their homes. What the future will be look like for children with no schools, women not secure, sources of income not found any more, shattered families among several countries, lost hope and generations. The authors who are researcher in the Syrian Center for Polices Studies are trying to put solutions for those who moved inside Syria and who crossed the prodders to Turkey and other countries and remote continents.

9. Bircan, T., & Sunata, U. (2015). Educational assessment of Syrian refugees in Turkey. *Migration Letters*, 12(3), 226.

This article is important because it shows that in the political, social and economic terms, Turkey is the most affected country of the Syrian crisis. More importantly, Turkey as a host country of Syrian refugees has been living a dramatic demographic change. The most marginalized group living in Turkey is children. Refugee education has hence become of top priority. The global report in refugee education is below the critical level, but Turkish report is even worse in the contexts of not only accessibility and quality. The article's main purpose is elaborating the current educational assessment of Syrian child refugees in Turkey. Our findings indicate the significant number of refugee children in need of access to basic education at all levels and underlines the magnitude of scarce of education program development mainly due to lack of financial matters. Hence, it advises a kind of collaboration among implementing public and private partners at the local, national and international levels.

Tuba Birican is a senior research associate in HIVA Education and Lifelong Learning Research Group in University of Leuven Belgium. Ulas Sunata is an Associate Professor at the Department of Sociology of the Bahçeşehir University in Turkey.

10. Özden, S. (2013). *Syrian refugees in Turkey*. Migration Policy Centre (MPC). European University Institute, Florence

This article is about the Turkey's humanitarian activities toward Syrian refugees. It reflects the Turkish policy in the Syria conflict. Yet, it has become increasingly clear that the Turkish government has overestimated its capacities, and thus failed to deliver sufficient assistance to Syrian refugees on its territory. At the same time the government's handling of the refugee issue has led to stark tensions among Turkey's political and societal forces, as Turkey's border regions contend with increasing security and economic challenges.

Germany and its European partners should support Turkey in maintaining and improving services to Syrian refugees in Turkey, and in delivering aid more effectively to internally displaced persons (IDPs) inside Syria. They should also push Turkey to adopt a long-term strategy for dealing with Syrian refugees.

SenayOzdenis is a specialist researcher in the Middle East issue. She is Archival researcher and conducted some researches in Syria and Lebanon and at the National Archives and at the archives of Syrian and Palestinian political organizations.

11. Berti, B. (2015). The Syrian refugee crisis: Regional and human security implications. *Strategic Assessment*, 17(4), 41-53.

This article is discussing the political and social impact of the ongoing refugee crisis which should not be seen solely through the humanitarian lens. The author says that the successful tackling the emergency and boosting the long term resilience of both refugee and host communities is also a vital strategic priority to prevent the long term destabilization and implosion of the entire region of Syria.

Berti sees that the relative lethargy with which the international community has reacted to the challenge reflects a fundamental underestimation of the nature of the crisis and its long term regional repercussions in terms of regional stability and resilience, but also in relation to issues such as radicalization and the rise of uncontrolled migratory flows, two issues that have been at the forefront of the European security agenda for the Mediterranean. The article will help is showing the real human security implications of the Syrian refugees case.

Dr. Benedetta Berti is a foreign policy and security researcher, analyst, consultant, author and lecturer. Her work focuses on armed groups and internal wars, analyzing the impact of insecurity on civilians and studying how to build more peaceful and resilient communities.

12. Seeberg, P. (2016). The EU-Turkey March 2016 Agreement As a Model: New Refugee Regimes and Practices in the Arab Mediterranean and the Case of Libya. *Global Turkey in Europe, Working Paper 16*.

This article speaks about the EU-Turkey agreement of March 2016, including the so-called '1:1 mechanism'. The agreement constitutes a new and significant element in the international patchwork of regimes and practices that attempt to regulate the movements of refugees and migrants in the Mediterranean region and to secure the rights of refugees and migrants. Given that the EU-Turkey agreement has contributed to reducing significantly the flow of refugees and migrants arriving in the EU, it seems relevant to ask whether the model can be replicated in other Arab Mediterranean contexts where migrants and refugees play an important role in the relationship between the EU and partner states. German Chancellor Angela Merkel has indicated that she would like to see similar agreements with Egypt and Tunisia for instance.

Peter Seeberg is Associate Professor at the Centre for Contemporary Middle East Studies, University of Southern Denmark. He is also Director of Danish Jordanian University Cooperation, an academic cooperation effort with universities in Jordan funded by the Danish Ministry of Foreign Affairs.

13. Dinçer, O. B., Federici, V., Ferris, E., Karaca, S., Kirişçi, K., & Çarmıklı, E. Ö. (2013). *Turkey and Syrian refugees: The limits of hospitality*. International Strategic Research Organization (USAK).

USAK has been following the issue of Syrian refugees closely since the beginning of the crisis. The work consists of three parts. The first part of the project was a substantive policy brief providing an overview of Syria's humanitarian crisis. The second part, represented here, is an in-depth examination of the implications of Syrian refugees for Turkey and will be followed by a longer report on Turkey, the European Union and Syrian displacement. The third part focuses on strengthening coordination and cooperation between Gulf, regional and international actors working inside Syria. The humanitarian needs and emerging governance structures will be examined across Turkey. In a broad sense, this initiative seeks to complement the work of other scholars who concentrate on the military and political dimensions of the crisis. By focusing on humanitarian needs in Syria, a more comprehensive assessment of the present and future situation is possible.

Osman Bahadır Dinçer is the head of Arab World Studies Desk at the Center for Middle Eastern and African Studies, USAK. Vittoria Federici, is a research assistant in the Brookings Doha Center, Brookings Institution. Elizabeth Ferris, co-director of the Brookings-LSE Project on Internal Displacement and senior fellow in Foreign Policy, Brookings Institution.

14. Erlich, R. (2015). *Inside Syria: The backstory of their civil war and what the world can expect*. Arab Scientific Publishers, Inc.

Based on firsthand reporting from Syria and throughout the Middle East, *Inside Syria* unravels the complex dynamics underlying the Syrian Civil War. Through vivid, on-the-ground accounts and interviews with rebel leaders, regime supporters, and Syrian president Bashar al-Assad himself, veteran journalist Reese Erlich gives the reader a better understanding of this momentous power struggle and why it matters.

Through his many contacts inside Syria, the author reveals who is supporting Assad and why; he describes the agendas of the rebel factions; and he depicts in stark terms the dire plight of many ordinary Syrian people caught in the cross-fire. The book also provides insights into the role of the Kurds, the continuing influence of Iran, and the policies of American leaders who seem interested only in protecting US regional interests.

The book does a good job on describing the recent history of Syria and the current conflict. It seems balanced and shows how the current position of the US is one of no hope for a better country.

15. Nofal, M. (2010). *Turkish Return to Orient: New Attitudes of the Turkish Policy*. Arab Scientific Publishers, Inc.

The importance of this book is that its writer is one of the specialized people in the Turkish affairs. He had great contributions in this field long time ago. The time of this book is important. Now days, Turkey is existing in all of the conflicts in the Middle East. It conducts foreign policies that can make changes. The author shows the most important characteristic in the turning point of the Turkish strategy of the rise of Neo Ottomanism. He gives a historical background to the roots of the new Islamism in Turkey.

The relation between religion and politics in Turkey gives importance to the study. Other factors inter here, relations with regional counties, the crisis in Syria and its results where military interventions and refugees are the most important.

In brief, Turkey is the only country which is Middle Eastern, Asian, Islamic, European and NATO member. It has many major internal and external challenges, politically, economically, military, socially and demographically.

16. European Union, (2015/2016). *Official Statements of Agreements on Migration between the European Union and the Republic of Turkey*. Press releases, European Council. Brussels.

The official statements of agreements on migration between the European Union and the Republic of Turkey form the core of the Turkish actions towards the Syrian refugees. The importance of these documents comes from that they show the commitments between the two partners. The negotiations went upon expectations from both sides. The European Union expects to be protected from the refugees' floods. Meanwhile, Turkey expects to be closer to join the EU from one hand. From another hand, financial aid is expected to be paid to Turkey by EU. But, what is the situation of the Syrian refugees in that game?

17. Kayaoglu, A., Şahin-Mencütek, Z., & Erdoğan, M. M. (2021). Return Aspirations of Syrian Refugees in Turkey. *Journal of Immigrant & Refugee Studies*, 1-23.

The authors debated that Intentional return is proposed as a tough answer for mass displacements, yet little is had some significant awareness of how evacuees see their choices. This article talks about what drives the return goals of Syrian evacuees in Turkey. In view of the examination of quantitative and subjective information (2017-18), shows that numerous Syrians condition their profit from the arrangement of safety, shift in power, work valuable open doors in Syria. Be that as it may, their reconciliation in Turkey likewise matters, yet perplexingly, for bring goals back. In particular, saw and experienced separation and socio-social distance impact goals. These arise as backhanded ramifications of the financial, social, and social mix. This article shows the intricacy behind the return issue by propelling the conversation on the job of beginning nation related factors in displaced people's yearnings from one perspective, and the significance of the combination into the host country on the other. Our discoveries add to additional comprehension of the return-joining nexus, especially the effect of exiles' socio-mental encounters, in extended outcast circumstances.

18. Akcapar, S. K., & Simsek, D. (2018). The politics of Syrian refugees in Turkey: A question of inclusion and exclusion through citizenship. *Social Inclusion*, 6(1), 176-187.

The article says that Turkey started to get outcasts from Syria in 2011 and has since turned into the nation facilitating the largest number of evacuees, with more than 3.5 million Syrians and a portion of 1,000,000 individuals of different identities, predominantly from Afghanistan, Iraq, and Iran. A significant defining moment in regards to the legitimate status of Syrian outcasts has accompanied ongoing revisions to the Turkish citizenship regulation. In light of progressing scholarly discussions on mix and citizenship, this article will investigate these two ideas on account of Syrian evacuees in Turkey. We will contend that the change in the Turkish citizenship regulation is an immediate result of late relocation streams. We further contend that the citizenship choice is utilized both as a prize for gifted travelers with monetary and social capital and as a device to incorporate the other Syrians. It additionally reflects other social, political, and segment worries of the Turkish government. Utilizing our new ethnographic review with Syrians and nearby populaces in two principal displaced persons facilitating urban areas in Turkey, Istanbul, and Gaziantep, we will find the triumphs and shortcomings of this system by embodying the perspectives of Syrian exiles on acquiring Turkish citizenship and the responses of Turkish nationals.

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